

DETERMINING THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES ON BUSINESS AND PROPOSING METHODS OF RESPONDING TO THE PROBLEMS OF THE COMPANY'S DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the problems of identifying the impact of digital information technologies on business and proposing ways for companies to respond to the challenges of the digital economy, adapting the company's strategic management tools to the rapidly changing external environment resulting from the rapid development of the digital economy. This article covers the main trends in changing the digital business environment at the macro and micro levels, issues of increasing the efficiency of using the company's internal potential, and the specific features of competitive struggle based on the active use of information and communication technologies.*

Keywords: *digital economy, production, hyper-competition, innovation, informatization, information, communication, platform, process, services, activity, infrastructure.*

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена проблемам определения влияния цифровых информационных технологий на бизнес и предложения путей реагирования компаний на вызовы цифровой экономики, а также адаптации инструментов стратегического управления компанией к быстро меняющейся внешней среде, возникающей в результате стремительного развития цифровой экономики. В статье рассматриваются основные тенденции изменения цифровой бизнес-среды на макро- и микроуровнях, вопросы повышения эффективности использования внутреннего потенциала компании, а также особенности конкурентной борьбы, основанной на активном использовании информационно-коммуникационных технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая экономика, производство, гиперконкуренция, инновации, информатизация, информация, коммуникация, платформа, процесс, услуги, деятельность, инфраструктура.*

In the 21st century, digital technologies have firmly entered all areas of our lives. The development of information and communication devices, the development of various intelligent robot systems, the ability to work with increasingly large amounts of data had a serious impact on the direction [1].

The modern world cannot be imagined without information technologies, which have changed and facilitated various industries, opening up new market opportunities. The emergence of new digital infrastructures, the development of computer technologies and digital communications creates new opportunities in the field of information technologies, applies them to the socio-political and economic life of society, and forms a new system of the international economy. The digital economy is based on the production of electronic products and services by high-tech business structures and the implementation of these products through electronic commerce [2].

The digital economy is an activity in which the main factors of production are information presented in digital form and their processing and use in large volumes, which allows to increase various types of production, technologies, equipment, efficiency, quality and productivity. Storage, sale, supply and consumption of goods and services.

Economic relations and laws are the subject of digital economy. Relations are formed in the process of production, sharing, distribution and consumption of scientific and technical information through digital information technologies, and the development of these processes is governed by economic laws [3].

The relevance of the article is related to technological changes that create new features in the global economic system and in the economy of individual markets and enterprises. Digital technologies have led to a revolution in business. The new digital economy is based on fundamentally different rules from the traditional economy. Economic entities are forced to work in a constantly changing environment, and development in such conditions means constant adaptation of business to a dynamically changing environment at the strategic and tactical levels.

The purpose of the article is to determine the impact of digital information technologies on business and to propose ways for companies to respond to the problems of the digital economy. The digital economy has a major impact on manufacturing, commerce, transportation and financial services, education, healthcare, media, and more. Technologies empower people and organizations in a variety of ways, enabling ideas to be created and disseminated, developed and developed [4].

The development of the informational digital economy is inextricably linked with the process of developing the information market. The information market can be characterized as a system of economic, legal and organizational relations for buying and selling intellectual labor products on a commercial basis. With the growth of informatization and digitization of society, the information industry began to dominate the economy, production is becoming more and more innovative and intensive. The number of people employed in the field of information and communication technologies is increasing year by year. The main factor stimulating the informatization of society in recent decades is the growth of the availability of hardware and software, the development of network technologies. The rapid development of the information market was significantly influenced by the rapid growth of software products development business [5].

The development of the digital economy led to the emergence of a new type of competition - hypercompetition. Systemic elements of hypercompetition are multi-level and multi-dimensional, new knowledge (competencies), controllability, dynamism, flexibility, mobility, innovation, efficiency, etc., which determine the globalization advantages of world leaders and technologically advanced multinational companies. The information market uses special methods of competition of structures that perform non-universal functions of developing innovative technologies for the production, storage, processing and transmission of information to optimize business processes of organizations. At the microeconomic level, information and communication technologies (ICT) allow enterprises to optimize their business processes. At the macroeconomic level, the impact of ICT explains the need to choose new directions for the development of the economy of countries and regions that take into account the trends in the world economy, including its use. The digital economy is able to overcome a number of limitations inherent in the traditional economy [6].

Digital products can be copied and used by an unlimited number of people, and they do not lose their consumer properties, and these properties are often improved when exchanged and

shared. In this case, the material products cannot be used by more than one person at the same time and are subject to wear and tear during operation. Online stores allow you to avoid limitations in areas and, therefore, in the breadth of the assortment that are characteristic of conventional trading platforms [7].

As the impact of data on company management increases, further scrutiny of its use is required. Nowadays, it is becoming more and more difficult to solve the organizational and management problems of companies and to establish business processes. The digital economy has made a number of important changes in the activities of companies:

1. The emergence of an information production factor that has become an important resource;
2. An increase in production costs as commodity and factor data have a price;
3. Reduction of transaction costs by using ICT;
4. Increasing the importance of the human factor in the introduction of ICT-based production;
5. Reducing the importance of the uncertainty factor through the active use of information resources.

In the traditional economy, the producer played the main role in the relationship between the producer and the buyer, because he was responsible for the formation of product ideas. The buyer made a choice from a list of benefits that had already been produced and offered by the producer. In the digital economy, the modern buyer has the opportunity to be a participant in the process of creating new consumer value, creating ideas for new products and services [8].

Moving to closer relationships with consumers can be described as a logical step for manufacturing enterprises to change the business environment. Manufacturing companies are increasingly beginning to cooperate with the consumer in creating product designs, manufacturing products on an individual order, developing new product functionality, etc. The concept of “open innovation” developed by G. Chesbrough is also associated with the changes brought about by the digital economy. Open innovation can be traced in the process of actively involving consumer businesses in the process of creating innovations, in which companies use not only internal ideas, but also ideas from employees, but also ideas from external consumers. Knowledge is an important strategic asset in the digital economy. They play a key role in the stable economic development of companies in various fields. In this regard, it is appropriate to form new approaches to developing a business development strategy based on modern tools and methods of integrating corporate knowledge into the company’s management system. Knowledge management, as one of the most important types of activities in the management system, should be focused on the formation of intellectual values, the development of organizational, consumer and human capital of enterprises. Intensive use of intellectual assets provides opportunities for the formation of internal and external competences, which together constitute the system of the company's main competences. The development of the digital economy has a significant impact on the domestic and foreign business environment [9].

There are fundamental changes in the field of information and communication technologies, which are reflected in various directions of the company's activity. The Internet allows even new and small companies to sell their products worldwide. Companies can quickly emerge and grow with relatively small capital investments. Information technology helps to reduce costs, significantly increase labor productivity and productivity in almost all sectors of the economy. In the digital economy, the position of companies in the market is becoming more complex, risk and uncertainty are increasing in making strategic decisions. This situation is

connected with unstable conditions due to dynamic technological changes, increased competition, influence of the state on the economy. The technological changes inherent in the digital economy are creating new market rules of business for producers and buyers. In the digital economic environment, companies must constantly seek new competitive strategies and improve their competitive performance. In order to survive and develop in the new conditions, companies must improve their skills in the field of digital information technologies [10].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

To identify the impact of digital information technologies on business and propose ways for companies to respond to the challenges of the digital economy. The digital economy has a major impact on manufacturing, commerce, transportation and financial services, education, healthcare, media, and more. Technologies empower people and organizations in a variety of ways, enabling ideas to be created and disseminated, developed and developed. Choosing one of the relevant models of digital technology in business, i.e., process, network, technological models, allows to specify the work to be performed in business enterprises, to increase efficiency consistently and through a clearly defined action plan. There are fundamental changes in the field of information and communication technologies, which are reflected in various directions of the company's activity. The Internet even allows new and small companies to market their products worldwide.

Information technologies help to reduce costs, significantly increase productivity and productivity in almost all sectors of the economy. In the digital economy, the position of companies in the market is becoming more complicated, risk and uncertainty in making strategic decisions are increasing. This situation is connected with the unstable conditions due to dynamic changes at the technological level, increased competition, and the state's influence on the economy. The technological changes inherent in the digital economy are creating new market rules of business for producers and buyers. In the digital economic environment, companies must constantly seek new competitive strategies and improve their competitive performance. In order to survive and develop in the new conditions, companies must improve their skills in the field of digital information technologies.

The effectiveness of using digital technologies in the digital economy and business shows that it is developing simultaneously in a wide range of fields and is not usually built by a limited number of companies, even if they are given special powers and resources. Therefore, the main role of using digital technologies in the digital economy and business should be occupied by private businesses with a strong entrepreneurial and innovative approach, and the state should be engaged in creating infrastructure and conditions for private initiative.

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